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An Approximation Applying the Euler-Mascheroni Theorem

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Abstract

We present an approximation for the natural logarithm of any positive real number, using the Euler-Mascheroni Theorem and a linear interpolation to approximate the value of the harmonic number corresponding to this real number.

keywords: Euler-Mascheroni constant, harmonic number, interpolation

The most updated version of this white paper is available at
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Introduction

1. This article primarily relies on references [1–4].
2. The Euler-Mascheroni Theorem establishes the relationship between harmonic sums and the Euler-Mascheroni constant (γ).
3. The Euler-Mascheroni constant was defined in 1735 by the Swiss mathematician Leonhard Euler [1]. In 1790, the Italian mathematician Lorenzo Mascheroni introduced the notation γ for this constant.

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4. The mathematical constant γ appears in various areas of analysis, number theory, and other disciplines, particularly in topics related to series, integrals, and theorems involving the distribution of prime numbers.
5. Although it is a widely studied constant, many properties of γ remain unknown. For instance, it is still uncertain whether γ is an irrational or transcendental number, which remains an open question. In light of this, the importance of the Euler-Mascheroni constant in various areas of mathematics is emphasized, highlighting its connection with other constants and special functions.

Preliminaries

6. For $m \in \mathbb{N}$, we define the m th harmonic number, H_m , as the sum:

$$H_m = 1 + \frac{1}{2} + \dots + \frac{1}{m}.$$

7. **Lemma A.** For $m \in \mathbb{N}$,

$$\frac{1}{m+1} < \ln\left(1 + \frac{1}{m}\right) < \frac{1}{m}.$$

8. Indeed, note that

$$\ln\left(1 + \frac{1}{m}\right) = \int_1^{1+\frac{1}{m}} \frac{1}{x} dx < \int_1^{1+\frac{1}{m}} \frac{1}{x} dx < \int_1^{1+\frac{1}{m}} dx = \frac{1}{m}.$$

9. On the other hand,

$$\ln\left(1 + \frac{1}{m}\right) = \int_1^{1+\frac{1}{m}} \frac{1}{x} dx > \int_1^{1+\frac{1}{m}} \frac{1}{1+\frac{1}{m}} dx = \frac{1}{m+1}.$$

10. Therefore,

$$\frac{1}{m+1} < \ln\left(1 + \frac{1}{m}\right) < \frac{1}{m}.$$

□

11. **Theorem A.** (See Theorem 16 in Chapter 4 from [3]). Let $(x_n)_{n \in \mathbb{N}}$ be a sequence with $x_n \geq 0$ for all $n \in \mathbb{N}$. The series $\sum_{k=1}^{\infty} x_k$ converges if, and only if, the sequence $(s_n)_{n \in \mathbb{N}}$ of its partial sums is bounded.

Teorema (Euler-Mascheroni)

12. For $m \in \mathbb{N}$,

$$\lim_{m \rightarrow +\infty} (H_m - \ln m) = \gamma.$$

13. γ is a positive constant known as the *Euler-Mascheroni constant*.

14. We start the proof by noting that

$$\begin{aligned} H_m - \ln m &= H_m - \sum_{j=1}^{m-1} [\ln(j+1) - \ln j] \\ &= \sum_{j=1}^{m-1} \left[\frac{1}{j} - \ln \left(1 + \frac{1}{j} \right) \right] + \frac{1}{m}. \end{aligned}$$

15. By Lemma A presented in (7), for $j \in \mathbb{N}$, we have

$$\ln \left(1 + \frac{1}{j} \right) < \frac{1}{j}.$$

16. Hence, we obtain the sequence $(x_j)_{j \in \mathbb{N}}$ with

$$x_j = \frac{1}{j} - \ln \left(1 + \frac{1}{j} \right) > 0 \quad \text{para todo } j \in \mathbb{N}.$$

17. This sequence allows us to define the series

$$\sum_{j=1}^{\infty} \left[\frac{1}{j} - \ln \left(1 + \frac{1}{j} \right) \right].$$

18. Thus, again by (7), the partial sums of this series satisfy

$$s_{m-1} = \sum_{j=1}^{m-1} \left[\frac{1}{j} - \ln \left(1 + \frac{1}{j} \right) \right] < \sum_{j=1}^{m-1} \left[\frac{1}{j} - \frac{1}{j+1} \right].$$

19. Consequently, $s_{m-1} < 1 - \frac{1}{m} < 1$ for all $m \in \mathbb{N}$.

20. By Theorem A presented in (11), we conclude that the series defined in (17) converges to a number γ .

21. Therefore, applying the limit in the second equality of (14) as $m \rightarrow +\infty$, we obtain

$$\lim_{m \rightarrow +\infty} (H_m - \ln m) = \gamma.$$

□

22. Further details about the Euler-Mascheroni Theorem can be found in [4, Theorem 5.19].

Approximation of $\ln x$

23. By the Euler-Mascheroni Theorem given in (12), we have the approximation

$$\ln m \cong H_m - \gamma.$$

24. Note that this approximation becomes better as $m \in \mathbb{N}$ increases.

25. The value of the *Euler-Mascheroni constant* to six decimal places is $\gamma \cong 0.577216$.

Generalization for any positive real x

26. For any $x \in \mathbb{R}$ with $x > 0$, consider its integer part defined by $\lfloor x \rfloor$ (floor function).

27. To determine an approximation for H_x , we perform a linear interpolation (see [2]), between $H_{\lfloor x \rfloor}$ and $H_{\lfloor x \rfloor + 1}$:

$$\frac{H_x - H_{\lfloor x \rfloor}}{H_{\lfloor x \rfloor + 1} - H_{\lfloor x \rfloor}} \cong \frac{x - \lfloor x \rfloor}{\lfloor x \rfloor + 1 - \lfloor x \rfloor}.$$

28. Thus,

$$H_x \cong H_{\lfloor x \rfloor} + (x - \lfloor x \rfloor) \cdot (H_{\lfloor x \rfloor + 1} - H_{\lfloor x \rfloor}).$$

29. Identifying $m = \lfloor x \rfloor$, we have

$$H_x \cong H_m + (x - m) \cdot (H_{m+1} - H_m),$$

where $x - m$ is the fractional part of x .

30. Let x be any positive real number. From (23) and (29), to determine an approximation for $\ln x$, we use the formula

$$\ln x \cong H_x - \gamma.$$

Example: Approximation of $\ln(10001.7)$

31. Let $x = 10001.7$, its integer part is determined by $m = \lfloor x \rfloor = 10001$.

32. Now, we calculate the harmonic numbers H_{10001} e H_{10002} , using

$$H_m = \sum_{j=1}^m \frac{1}{j}.$$

33. Thus,

$$H_{10001} = 1 + \frac{1}{2} + \frac{1}{3} + \dots + \frac{1}{10001},$$

$$H_{10002} = H_{10001} + \frac{1}{10002}.$$

34. Consequently,

$$H_{10001} \cong 9.787606,$$

$$H_{10002} \cong 9.787705.$$

35. The fractional part of $x = 10001.7$ is

$$x - \lfloor x \rfloor = x - m = 0.7$$

36. Performing the linear interpolation between H_{10001} and H_{10002} , from (29), we obtain

$$H_{10001.7} \cong H_{10001} + 0.7 \cdot (H_{10002} - H_{10001}).$$

37. Hence,

$$H_{10001.7} \cong 9.787675.$$

38. Using the formula given in (30), for $x = 10001.7$, we have

$$\ln(10001.7) \cong H_{10001.7} - \gamma.$$

39. Therefore,

$$\ln(10001.7) \cong 9.210459.$$

40. The *exact value* of $\ln(10001.7)$ to six decimal places is **9.210444**.
41. The *approximate value* determined by the formula given in (30) is **9.210459**, which is very close to the exact value, with a *difference* of only **0.000015**.

Final Remarks

42. In this article, a method that utilizes the Euler-Mascheroni Theorem in conjunction with linear interpolation was presented to approximate the natural logarithm of a positive real number. The simplicity of this method stands out due to its effective application in mathematical analysis problems, particularly those involving harmonic series and integrals.
43. The proposed approach demonstrates high accuracy in approximation, especially as the real number increases, as shown by the numerical example provided, where the difference between the approximated and exact values is small.
44. A promising avenue for future research would be the extension of this technique to other transcendental functions, beyond the natural logarithm.

Open Invitation

*Review, add content to, and co-author this white paper [5, 6].
Join the **Open Mathematics Collaboration**.*

Supplementary Files

[7]

How to Cite this White Paper

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Agreement

All authors are in agreement with the guidelines presented in [6].

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